

THE INFLUENCE OF HUMAN RESOURCE ALLOCATION ON PERFORMANCE OF MONITORING AND EVALUATION SYSTEM OF CHILD PROTECTION PROJECTS AT WORLD VISION, KENYA

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ABSTRACT

There is low utilization of the progress reports from monitoring and evaluation system of the child protection projects at World Vision Kenya. More specifically, less than 10% of the monitoring and evaluation progress reports generated periodically is utilized by the stakeholders. About 40% of the progress reports at World Vision Kenya are not prepared within the established costs, creating cost overruns within the monitoring and evaluation function at World Vision Kenya. The available human resource limitations have comprised the quality and timeliness of the progress reports with regard to child protection projects at World Vision, Kenya. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the influence of human resource allocation on performance of monitoring and evaluation system of child protection projects at World Vision, Kenya. A descriptive design was adopted targeting 9 child protection projects by World Vision Kenya as the unit of analysis and 220 staff from World Vision Kenya at its head quarter in Nairobi as the unit of observation. The sample size was 141 participants. Primary data was collected through questionnaire that was pilot tested among 10 respondents from Save-the-Children. Content and construct validity were adopted while Cronbach Alpha was used to establish reliability. The collected data was processed as aided by SPSS tool supported by descriptive frequencies and percentages) and inferential statistics (regression analysis). It was established that human resource allocation was practiced at World Vision Kenya and significantly contributed towards performance of the M&E system of the child protection projects. The study concludes that human resources are critical when it comes to performance of M&E system in a project organization. The study recommends that the project managers of the child project projects at WVK should ensure that the M&E teams have relevant diversity in terms of gender and age to effectively dispense their duties.

Keywords: Human Resource Allocation, Project Performance

INTRODUCTION

Performance of the monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system is a relatively new concept that is still evolving and it is affected by challenges of resource allocation. Some of the underlying issues in resource allocation that have far reaching influence on performance of the M&E system include human resource, financial and technology related resources. This assertion was

echoed by Sadiq (2019) who noted that resources comprises of technologies, finances, physical facilities and time besides people who play a key role in addressing many issues related with failure of M&E systems. Resources enable the M&E systems of the project organization to run and thus allocation of the resources to the project entities should be done with care. Although allocation of resources in a project organization can be a tough undertaking, careful practice can help an organization to have access to the needed resources. Resource allocation is a relevant process when it comes to sound performance of the M&E system. It is very difficult for a project organization to operationalize and run its M&E system when the resources have not been allocated for the same purpose. Hence, proper performance of the M&E system requires an organization to allocate sufficient resources (Abalang, 2016).

On a global scale, Mark and Pfeiffer (2011) shared that the M&E system of the United States (US) government supports budgeting and management decisions done on a day to day basis. In India, Mehrotra (2013) shared that the increased public expenditure has increased the demand for M&E system from donor agencies and the government in general. In Brazil, Sellera, Brito, Jovanovic, Rodrigues, Oliveira, Santos and Moraes (2019) noted that continuous M&E activities help project organizations to measure and track strategically established information while improving on the quality of the established indicators of the projects. Focusing on China, Chen (2009) orated that most projects in urban planning are supported by strong and well performing M&E systems.

Regionally in Ghana, Kissi, Agyekum, Baiden, Tannor, Asamoah and Andam (2019) argued that existence of sound M&E system enhances the overall performance of the project. In South Africa, Ronette and Tania (2010) indicated that performance of the M&E system is affected by a number of issues including political leadership, inability to manage change issues and concerns about capacity building of the staff. Furthermore, Abrahams (2015) argued that in South Africa, there is a well-established official ministry responsible for issues of M&E in the country with other similar countries including Ghana, Benin and Uganda. In Tanzania, most of the non-governmental organizations do not have the requisite financial and human resources for proper functioning of their M&E systems with the issue of poor budgetary allocation and understaffing to perform the M&E activities (Mjingo, 2017). Uganda is one of the countries in East Africa with well-developed M&E frameworks that allow NGOs to carry out their project activities (Holvoet & Inberg, 2014).

Locally in Kenya, Wambua (2019) noted that sound M&E systems enhance the overall functioning of the project organization. Odhiambo, Wakibia and Sakwa (2020) argued that tracking of progress and timeliness are salient practices of any M&E system in a project organization. Proper performance of the M&E system requires the project managers to marshal the resources behind the M&E function in a project organization. Inadequate resources were slowing down performance of the M&E system of the organization while excessive funding was resulting into wastage of the resources of the organization. Thus, resources allocation should a well thought process with the aim of contributing towards performance of the M&E systems in place (Muchelule, Otonde & Achayo, 2017).

Performance of the M&E system has received close attention among scholars around the world. However, a clear interplay between resource allocation and performance of these M&E systems

has remained poorly understood and conceived. In particular, the role played by allocation of finances, technologies, people and materials as dimensions of resource allocation and their relevance in driving performance of the M&E systems in both developed and less developed economies around the world including Kenya has remained under-researched (Sopha & Asih, 2018). Thus, this study was to provide the link existing between resource allocation and performance of the M&E system.

While monitoring is an ongoing process that allows the project organization to gather and process data with the key role of controlling the program (Mtshali, 2015), evaluation is an independent and systematic exercises that assess either completed or ongoing projects including the implementation phase and the results (Musonera & Mulyungi, 2016). Therefore, M&E is a process where data is systematically collected and analyzed on the ongoing programs and it is carried out through the system. There has been growing demands among stakeholders to safeguard performance of the M&E systems in a project organization. Stakeholders are always demanding for accountability in used of resources and the related impact of the project and this is what has heightened the need to adopt M&E systems in project organization.

As noted by Kasule (2016), the M&E system is an important factor if the project is to meet its formulated goals. However, performance of the M&E system has been a concern among different projects around the world. According to Paru (2019), one of the key challenges of affecting performance of the M&E is that there are no clearly established parameters for determining the quality as a proxy of M&E system. In Bangladesh, neither the government nor the non-governmental organizations do own the M&E systems. In Ghana, the M&E system has been considered by the government as a critical tool for managing intervention hence subjectivity.

The M&E systems comprise of humans and these people create the whole difference in the project organization (Jin, 2019). The role played by human resources in performance of the M&E systems cannot therefore be overlooked. The M&E system should be supported by competent and qualified team and these should be regularly trained. As noted by Alipouri-Sakha, Mohtasham and Mostafavi (2018), success of the M&E system largely depends on the people in place with less support of the system related factors. Rewards either in monetary or non-monetary terms are also key issues when an organization seeks to enhance performance of its M&E system (Khanizad & Montazer, 2018). Poorly rewarded and less motivated M&E staff would compromise the quality of information obtained from the M&E exercises in the project organization (Momeni & Martinsuo, 2018).

Child protection has emerged as an important social issue in the modern world since children are vulnerable and they are increasingly undergoing violence and exploitation. As a concept, child protection has been understood in different ways by the various agencies handling the welfare of the children. As such, this term has attracted different definitions on the basis of the various organizations involved in safeguarding the welfare of the children. Child protection has received a global attention, especially with the establishment of the instruments aimed at protecting the rights of the children around the world. These include the UNCRC formed in 1989 and the ACRWC established in 1999. In Africa, the activities of UNHCR are complemented by the

CRWC that the African Union (AU) adopted in the year 1990. All these instruments have specific provisions that protect children against all manner of economic exploitation.

Kenya is a signatory of UNCRC and ACRWC treaties and it has a fully operational Children Act 2001. Besides, there is the 2010 constitution that has specific provisions which protect the rights of the children in Kenya. All these Provisions are complemented by different non-governmental organizations that are operating in Kenya to protect and safeguard the rights of the children. The rise of NGOs in child protection stems from the popular media reports which have indicated the serious problems posed by exploitation and violence against children. Some of the popular organizations operating in Kenya to protect the rights of children include UNICEF, SIDA, and Save the Children, Terre des homes, Plan International and World Vision among other organizations (NGO Coordination Board, 2020).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The M&E system of World Vision is facing challenges as far as its performance is concerned. For instance, less than 10% of the M&E progress reports generated periodically is utilized by the stakeholders. About 40% of the progress reports at WVK are not prepared within the established costs, creating cost overruns within the M&E function at WVK (Muyomba, 2014). To enhance performance of the M&E system, the project managers of the organization should allocate sufficient financial, technological, human and material resources to the M&E function of the organization (Muchelule et al., 2017). However, at present, allocation of funds towards the M&E system of at WVK is not thorough enough. The M&E staffs are not adequate and budget constraints have remained a challenge at WVK (Jean, 2018).

The specific emphasis on child protection projects (CPPs) stem from the rising cases of abuse, neglect and violence on children that has remained a global challenge. Issues affecting the children have risen in the society as documented by different media reports (UNICEF, Kenya report 2014). Although different projects have been implemented in Kenya in regards to child protection, the study conducted by UNICEF-Kenya (2014) pointed out that performance of the M&E systems of these programs is underperforming. This is occasioned by the challenge of inadequate resource allocation. For the case of WVK, a number of child protection programs have been operating in Kenya in 21 counties for a long period of time. However, to date, there is no clearly documented status report of these child protection projects raising questions on whether performance of the M&E system is satisfactory enough.

Different studies have been carried out to on resource allocation and performance of M&E system in different contexts. Juma (2015) did an inquiry into factors that influence the ability of Kenyan banks to utilize M&E systems. The variables covered by the inquiry included resource allocation, staff training and managerial commitment and all were found to have an influence on utilization of M&E system. Njama (2015) focused on bringing out the key issues that shape the degree of effectiveness within M&E system and covered availability of funds, stakeholder participation and leadership at the organizational level. The study conducted by Gitau and Kibuine (2020) focused on organizational resource allocation and its link with performance of the firm where the results were that allocation of resources is significantly connected with ability of the firms to perform.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

This study was guided Resource Based View Theory advanced by Penrose (1959), this theory links resources with ability to remain competitive. Barney (2001) share effective utilization of the resources including the staff in the project organization can lead to better performance. In order to perform, the firm should have resources that cannot easily be copied by other rivals (Park, Seo, Hong, Shin, Hwa & Bae, 2015). Thus, a project organization needs to effectively take care of the resources in place to ensure better performance. Capabilities are different from resources in the firm (Guo& Li, 2019). Resources that are too specific in their nature are regarded as capabilities. Resources are tangible and intangible facilities owned by an entity. Capability is the manner in which these resources are deployed in an entity. This is the main theory of the study since it supported the independent variable resource allocation. Thus, the theory is used to link resource allocation and performance of M&E system. In other words, resources are important for proper functioning of the M&E system in a project organization.

Empirical Review

Dwivedula (2019) conducted a study on the HR management in the context of project management. The study reviewed literature that showed that HR management is an important concept when it comes to management of the project activities. A total of 104 peer reviewed article journals were reviewed in this study where six themes revolving around HR were identified. These themes that were identified from the review of the journals in this inquiry include the fact the project managers is an enabler of success of the project, human resources are vehicles of competitiveness of the projects, human resources drive innovation in projects, people management competencies and contextual competencies of the project manager all inform the success of the project. This study creates conceptual gap since it failed to link HR allocation with performance of the M&E systems.

The study conducted by Sopha and Asih (2018) focused on human resource allocation in humanitarian entities. The study was informed by the assertion that human resources were believed to be the most relevant factor when it came to the way humanitarian entities carried out their operations. The essence of the inquiry was to dwell on bringing out the key policy of allocating human resources in such organizations. The inquiry leveraged on the systematic dynamics approach to come up with a simulation model that inform the policy of allocating human resources in the humanitarian entities. The inquiry developed and tested two incidences; empirical relief demand and constant relief demand. A number of experiments were carried out in bringing out the various policies used in allocation of human resources across these two scenarios. It was shown that a trade off in allocation of human resources existed between the activities of building capacity and the relief operations of the humanitarian organizations. Thus, the study inferred that allocation of human resource capacity is key in sustaining the relief operations of the humanitarian entities on a long term horizon. Although this study covered the issues of HR allocation, it failed to link these with performance of the M&E systems hence the gap.

Arias, Saavedra, Marques, Munoz-Gama and Sepúlveda (2018) did an inquiry on human resource allocation within the management of the processes in the business. The study was

supported by review of past journals and periodicals covering the period of 2005 all through to 2016. In total, 2,370 articles were reviewed in this study out of which 75 of them were selected for inclusion in the inquiry. The finding from the study was that human resource allocation is an area of research that is still emerging with validation and evaluation being the two main type of research in this area. Evaluation within the area of human resource allocation has largely been done through two methods being case studies and simulation.

Kwizera (2018) used a case of United States International University-Africa to determine the role that strategic HRM practices play as far as the ability of staff to perform is concerned. The variables of the study included financial rewards, manager’s attitudes and organizational culture. The results from this study were that financial reward, manager’s attitudes and organizational culture all have an influence on employee performance. The study looked at strategic HRM practices, where HR allocation could only be a subset and their link with staff performance. The present study was to focus specifically on HR allocation and its link with performance of the M&E system.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 show the relationship between variables whereby the independent variable is the human resource allocation which is measured in terms of skills and competency, teamwork, delegation, team composition & diversity. The dependent variable is performance of monitoring and evaluation system which is measured in terms of progress reports, timelines, cost and quality.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive design was adopted targeting 9 child protection projects by World Vision Kenya as the unit of analysis and 220 staff from World Vision Kenya at its head quarter in Nairobi as the unit of observation. The sample size was 141 participants. Primary data was collected through questionnaire that was pilot tested among 10 respondents from Save-the-Children. Content and construct validity were adopted while Cronbach Alpha was used to establish reliability. The collected data was processed as aided by SPSS tool supported by descriptive frequencies and percentages) and inferential statistics (regression analysis).

FINDINGS

The study sought to investigate the influence of human resource allocation on performance of monitoring and evaluation system of child protection projects at World Vision, Kenya. The findings are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Human Resource Allocation

	Mean	Std. Dev
The staff have requisite skills to carry out M&E activities of the CPPs in this organization	3.78	.975
The staff working on M&E activities of the CPPs have the required competency	4.12	.794
Teamwork is highly promoted among staff working on M&E activities of CPPs in this organization	3.61	1.045
Senior staff working on M&E of the CPPs delegate duties to their junior staff in this organization	3.90	.737
The team carrying out M&E activities of the CPPs is diverse	3.43	.744
Average	3.77	.859

Source: Field Data (2021)

Table 4.3 gives an average value of 3.77; this means human resource allocation was practiced at WVK. The highly scored aspect of HR allocation was the fact that the staff working on M&E activities of the CPPs had the required competency (M=4.12). This finding is supported by Jin (2019) who shared that the M&E systems comprise of humans and these people create the whole difference in the project organization and that the role played by human resources in performance of the M&E systems cannot therefore be overlooked. Respondents agreed that senior staff working on M&E of the CPPs delegated duties to their junior staff (M=3.90). The staff had requisite skills to carry out M&E activities of the CPPs (M=3.61). This finding is supported by Njeru and Luketero (2018) operationalized performance of the M&E system into skills of the M&E team. This means that the skills of the M&E team are critical towards its success. However, the diversity of the project team was moderately scored (M=3.43).

Results of Inferential Statistics Analysis

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

		Human resource allocation	Project performance
Human resource allocation	Pearson Correlation	1	.261
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.012
	N	93	93
Project performance	Pearson Correlation	.566	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	93	93

Source: Research Data (2020)

Table 2 gives correlation results where human resource allocation ($r=.261$) had a moderate and positive relationship with performance of the M&E system. Equally, Sopha and Asih (2018) shared that a trade off in allocation of human resources existed between the activities of building capacity and the relief operations of the humanitarian organizations.

Table 3: Model Summary of Regression Analysis

Table 4.1: Regression Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.796 ^a	.633	.617	1.51383

Source: Field Data (2021)

Table 4.3 gives R^2 value of .633, whose implication is that 63.3% change in performance of the M&E of the child protection projects at World Vision, Kenya is explained by the human resource allocation practices in place.

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination of the Variable

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.856	1.830		2.107	.038
	Human resource allocation	.131	.064	.033	2.047	.033

At 5% level of significance, Table 4.13 shows that HR allocation ($\beta=.131$, $p<0.05$ & $t>1.96$) has significant effect on performance of M&E system of the child protection projects at WVK. This finding is supported by Dwivedula (2019) who observed that human resources are vehicles of competitiveness of the projects.

The resulting regression equation was $Y = 3.856 + 0.131X_1$

Where Y = Project Performance
 X_1 = Human Resource Allocation

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that human resources are critical when it comes to performance of M&E system in a project organization. Any project organization that wishes to enhance performance of M&E system should therefore be ready to allocate adequate human resources. These human resources include a combination of people, their specific expertise and experience that are needed for proper performance of a M&E system.

The study has acknowledged the significant role played by human resource allocation in performance of the M&E system. Thus, the project managers of the child project projects at WVK should ensure that the M&E teams have relevant diversity in terms of gender and age to effectively dispense their duties.

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